

Leaf water potential (LWP) of upland rice breeding lines and varieties in an irrigated field in Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1988.

Variety or line	LWP (MPa)
BR4290-3-1-10	- 0.75
BR4290-3-3-5	- 1.24
BR1888-29-2-2-3	- 1.00
BR1888-29-2-3-4	- 1.00
BR1890-12-2-1-1	- 1.11
BR1890-1-1-1-2	- 1.14
BR20	- 0.90
BR21	- 0.92
<i>F-test</i>	184.42**
LSD (0.05)	0.04

Stress tolerance — excess water

Germination and seedling development of floating rice at different soil moisture regimes

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Farmers usually dry seed floating rices before the onset of monsoon rains. In certain years, when the monsoon is early, dry seeding is not possible. Also, dry seeding is followed by drought, and farmers may have to replant a wet seeded rice.

We studied germination and growth of floating rice under different moisture regimes at crop establishment. Dry seeds and pregerminated seeds of Pin Gaew 56, a Thai floating rice, were planted at 100 seeds/tray in 25- × 33- × 10-cm plastic trays filled with 7 kg Maahas clay soil. Four soil moisture regimes were applied, with three replications (see table).

The pregerminated seeds emerged first. However, differences in percentage

Emergence of Pin Gaew 56 seedlings under different soil moisture regimes.^a IRRI greenhouse, 1990.

Soil moisture	Emergence (%) at 7 DAS	
	Dry seed	Pregerminated seed
Field capacity	98 a	98 a
Saturated	95 ab	95 ab
2 cm clear water	67 c	87 b
2 cm muddy water	71 c	74 c

^aIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

of emergence between dry seeds and pregerminated seeds 7 d after sowing (DAS) were small. Field capacity and saturated soil moisture favored seedling emergence. As little as 2 cm excess water significantly decreased emergence. Pregerminated seeds emerged poorly in muddy water.

Growth and development were vigorous at field capacity and at saturation (see figure). However, seedlings from pregerminated seeds tended to grow and develop better in saturated soil than at field capacity. Standing 2-cm-deep water significantly retarded seedling growth and development.

The effects were more-pronounced in seedlings from dry seed than from pregerminated seed. Muddy water at seeding did not have much effect on growth and development at later stages because the water cleared within 24 h.

The results indicate that field capacity or saturated soil moisture regime is favorable for germination, growth, and development of both dry and pregerminated seeds. Broadcasting dry seeds of floating rice is recommended, but pregerminated seeds could be an alternative in very wet or extremely low areas where rainwater accumulates during sowing. ■

Shoot and root dry weight of rice seedlings germinated under different soil moisture regimes. IRRI greenhouse, 1990.

Stress tolerance — adverse temperature

Screening rice cultivars at reproductive stage for low temperature tolerance in western Nepal

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Injury due to low temperature is a major constraint to improvement of rice production in the 1,000-2,000 m high areas of Nepal. No improved variety has yet been developed for elevations above 1,400 m.

In 1987 and 1988, we evaluated rice cultivars at three altitudes. The materials

were from IRRI; the National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur; Department of Agricultural Botany (DOAB); and local germplasm collected from 1,000-2,300 m altitudes in the western hills.

In 1987, the materials were evaluated at Tapu (1,000 m), Lumle (1,400 m), and Chhomro (2,000 m) to identify varietal differences in low temperature tolerance and altitude and the highest limit of varietal adaptation. In 1988, materials identified as promising from the 1987 trials were assessed at Tapu. Sera (1,250 m), and Lumle. Test cultivars were planted in rows in 1.2-m² plots, at 20- ×